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Supplementary Material

Disease severity in coinfecting hosts: the importance of infection order

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Supplementary tables and figures

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22 Table S1. Primer sequences used for the RT-qPCR.

Target	Forward sequence (5' to 3')	Reverse sequence (5' to 3')
β -Actin	ATGGAGGGGAATACAGCCC	TTCTTTGCAGTCCTTCGTT
GAPDH	CTCCCACTCTCCACCTTCG	GCCTCTCTTGCTCAGTGTC
Hmox-1	GCCGAGAATGCTGAGTTCATG	TGGTACAAGGAAGCCATCACC
IFN- γ	GAGCTCATTGAATGCTTGGC	GCGTCATTGAATCACACCTG
IL-10	AAGGCTTGGAACCCAAGTAACCC	TGCACTACCAAAGCCACAAGGCAG
TGF- β 1	CCCAGTCTCCATACATTAACCC	CACCATCACCTTGAACCTCTGAC

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25 Table S2. 27-color spectral flow cytometry panel used for the staining of mouse splenocytes.

Emission (nm)	Target	Fluorophore	Clone	Supplier	Cat. ID
<i>Viability</i>					
473	/	LIVE/DEAD Blue	/	Invitrogen	L23105
<i>Surface markers</i>					
388	CD45	BUV395	30-F11	BD Bioscience	564279
496	CD80	BUV496	16-10A1	BD Bioscience	741091
563	F4/80	BUV563	T45-2342	BD Bioscience	749284
615	CD19	BUV615	1D3	BD Bioscience	751213
661	CD8 α	BUV661	53-6.7	BD Bioscience	750023
737	LAG-3	BUV737	C9B7W	BD Bioscience	741820
805	CD11b	BUV805	M1/70	BD Bioscience	741934
421	CTLA-4	BV421	UC10-4B9	BioLegend	106312
451	Ly6G	Pacific Blue	1A8	BioLegend	127612
506	PD-1	eFluor506	J43	ThermoFisher	69-9985-82
570	Ly6C	BV570	HK1.4	BioLegend	128030
605	CD3	BV605	17A2	BD Bioscience	564009
650	CD11c	BV650	N418	BioLegend	117339
711	CD127	BV711	A7R34	BioLegend	135035
750	NkP46	BV750	29A1.4	BD Bioscience	746875
786	CD49d	BV786	R1-2	BD Bioscience	564397
521	CD163	FITC	TNKUPJ	ThermoFisher	11-1631-82
710	PD-L1	PerCP-eFluor 710	MIH5	ThermoFisher	46-5982-82
660	CD11a	APC	M17/4	BioLegend	101120
700	CD4	AF700	RM4-5	BD Bioscience	557956
780	MHCII	APC-Cy7	M5/114.15.2	BioLegend	107628
<i>Intracellular markers</i>					
480	ki67	BV480	B56	BD Bioscience	566109
576	Tbet	PE	4B10	BD Bioscience	561265
610	RORyt	PE-CF594	Q31-378	BD Bioscience	562684
693	GATA3	BB700	L50-823	BD Bioscience	566642
774	FOXP3	PE-Cy7	FJK-16s	Invitrogen	25-5773-82

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29 Figure S1. Gating strategy used for the spectral flow cytometry analysis to separate mouse splenocyte
 30 subsets. a) Gating of live immune cells. (1) Time parameter to exclude microfluidic fluctuations.
 31 Selection of (2) splenocytes without debris and (3) singlets. Selection of (4) live LD-Blue⁻ and immune
 32 CD45⁺ cells. b) Gating of T lymphocyte subsets. Selection of (5) CD19⁺CD3⁻ B cells, (6) LIN⁻ cells and (7)
 33 CD19⁺CD3⁺ T cells. Selection of (8) CD8⁺ T cells, (9) CD4⁺CD8⁻ other T cells and (10) CD4⁺ T cells. Selection
 34 of (11) FoxP3⁺ Treg, (12) Tbet⁺ Th1, (13) GATA-3⁺ Th2 and (14) RORyt⁺ Th17 cell subsets within CD4⁺ T
 35 lymphocytes. c) Gating of B lymphocyte subsets. Selection of (15) CD127⁺ immature B cells and (16)
 36 Tbet⁺ memory B cells. d) Gating of LIN⁻ cells. Separation of (17) Ly6G⁺ neutrophils from (18) other LIN⁻
 37 cells. Selection of (19) non-myeloid LIN⁻ cells and (20) other myeloid cells. Separation of (21)
 38 MHCII^{high}CD11c^{high} dendritic cells from (22) non-dendritic other myeloid cells. Selection of (23)
 39 F4/80⁺CD11b⁻ red pulp macrophages, (24) F4/80⁺CD11b⁺ macrophages and (25) F4/80^{-/low}CD11b⁺
 40 monocytes. Selection of (26) MHCII⁺CD163⁻ red pulp macrophages and (27) MHCII⁺CD163⁺ scavenger
 41 red pulp macrophages. Selection of (28) MHCII^{-/low}Ly6C^{-/low}, (29) MHCII^{-/low}Ly6C^{int} and (30) MHCII^{-/low}
 42 Ly6C^{high} monocyte subsets.

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Figure S2. Gating strategy used for the spectral flow cytometry analysis to identify immune checkpoint markers within mouse splenocyte subsets. a) Gating of live immune cells. (1) Time parameter to exclude microfluidic fluctuations. Selection of (2) splenocytes without debris and (3) singlets. Selection of (4) live LD-Blue⁻ and immune CD45⁺ cells. b) Gating of T lymphocyte subsets. Selection of (5) CD19⁻ CD3⁺ T cells. Selection of (6) CD4⁺ T cells and (7) CD8⁺ T cells. Selection of (8) FoxP3⁺ Treg. Identification of (9) CTLA-4⁺ Treg cells. Identification of (10) PD-1⁺, (11) LAG-3⁺ and (12) CTLA-4⁺ cells from CD8⁺ T lymphocyte subset.

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57 Figure S3. Changes in body mass over the course of the infection. Body mass is expressed as percent
 58 change with respect to body mass at day 0 for the single infection and the simultaneous infection or
 59 the day of the last infection for the coinfection groups. a) Changes in body mass for single Py infected
 60 mice and coinfected (Hp+Py, Hp-7+Py, Hp-28+Py) mice; b) Changes in body mass for single Hp infected
 61 mice and coinfected (Py-14+Hp, Py-28+Hp) mice. Dots represent the raw data, the lines represent the
 62 fit of a GLMM, and the shaded area around the line the 95% CI.

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65 Table S3. General linear mixed model investigating the changes in body mass (percent change with
 66 respect to day 0) in single Py infected and coinfecting (Hp+Py, Hp-7+Py, Hp-28+Py) mice. We report the
 67 parameter estimates with the 95% CI, df (degrees of freedom), F and p values. Mouse ID was included
 68 as a random effect to take into account the non-independence of observations for the same individual
 69 over time. N = 156 individuals and 789 observations.
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Fixed effects		Estimate	95% CI	df	F	p
Treatment				3,625	2.32	0.0742
	Py	0				
	Hp+Py	5.2	1.14/9.25			
	Hp-7+Py	1.28	-2.74/5.3			
	Hp-28+Py	2.78	-1.33/6.9			
Time		0.544	0.35/0.74	1,625	73.10	<0.0001
Squared time		-0.004	-0.01/0.001	1,625	90.37	<0.0001
Time*Treatment				3,625	2.19	0.0882
	Py	0				
	Hp+Py	-0.84	-1.58/-0.1			
	Hp-7+Py	-0.04	-0.76/0.68			
	Hp-28+Py	-0.49	-1.22/0.24			
Squared Time*Treatment				3,625	1.70	0.1661
	Py	0				
	Hp+Py	0.01	-0.02/0.04			
	Hp-7+Py	-0.02	-0.05/0.007			
	Hp-28+Py	-0.01	0.04/0.017			
Random effect		Estimate	SE	z	p	
ID		17.7	2.58	6.87	<0.0001	

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73 Table S4. General linear mixed model investigating the changes in body mass (percent change with
74 respect to day 0 or the day of the last infection for the coinfection groups) in single Hp infected and
75 coinfecting (Py-14+Hp, Py-28+Hp) mice. We report the parameter estimates with the 95% CI, df
76 (degrees of freedom), F and p values. Mouse ID was included as a random effect to take into account
77 the non-independence of observations for the same individual over time. N = 115 individuals and 609
78 observations.
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Fixed effects		Estimate	95% CI	df	F	p
Treatment				2,488	2.47	0.086
	Hp	0				
	Py-14+Hp	0.37	-1.79/2.53			
	Py-28+Hp	2.36	0.15/4.57			
Time		0.55	0.40/0.70	1,488	16.88	<0.0001
Squared time		-0.003	-0.008/0.0004	1,488	2.86	0.0916
Time*Treatment				2,488	13.93	<0.0001
	Hp	0				
	Py-14+Hp	-0.50	-0.73/-0.28			
	Py-28+Hp	-0.54	-0.78/-0.31			
Squared Time*Treatment				2,488	5.41	0.0047
	Hp	0				
	Py-14+Hp	0.009	0.003/0.015			
	Py-28+Hp	0.009	0.003/0.016			
Random effect		Estimate	SE	z	p	
ID		11.50	1.9	6.07	<0.0001	

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82 Table S5. General linear mixed model investigating the changes in body mass (percent change with
 83 respect to the day of the last infection) in coinfecting mice depending on the order of infection (either
 84 Hp first or Py first). We report the parameter estimates with the 95% CI, df (degrees of freedom), F and
 85 p values. Mouse ID was included as a random effect to take into account the non-independence of
 86 observations for the same individual over time. N = 151 individuals and 720 observations
 87

Fixed effects		Estimate	95% CI	df	F	p
Treatment				1,565	5.40	0.0205
	Py first	0				
	Hp first	-2.79	-5.14/-0.43			
Time		0.26	-0.05/0.57	1,565	47.44	<0.0001
Squared time		-0.005	-0.018/0.009	1,565	60.10	<0.0001
Time*Treatment				1,565	20.63	<0.0001
	Py first	0				
	Hp first	1.0	0.57/1.43			
Squared Time*Treatment				1,565	45.74	<0.0001
	Py first	0				
	Hp first	-0.06	-0.08/-0.05			
Random effect		Estimate	SE	z	p	
ID		10.42	1.67	6.24	<0.0001	

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90 Table S6. General linear model investigating the changes in spleen mass (log mg) in non-infected, and
91 single (Hp, Py) infected mice. We report the type III sum of squares, degrees of freedom (df), the F and
92 p values. The R² of the model is 0.92. N = 117 individuals.
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Source of variation	Type III SS	df	F	p
Treatment	9.02	2,105	328.25	<0.0001
Time	4.32	3,105	104.82	<0.0001
Treatment*Time	3.92	6,105	47.49	<0.0001

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97 Figure S4. Changes in log₁₀ transformed spleen mass (mg) over the course of the infection. a) Changes
 98 in spleen mass for non-infected and single (Hp, Py) infected mice; b) Changes in spleen mass for non-
 99 infected, single Py infected and coinfecting (simultaneous infection and Hp first) groups; c) Changes in
 100 spleen mass for non-infected, single Hp infected and coinfecting (Py first) groups; d) Changes in spleen
 101 mass for coinfecting groups depending on the order of the infection (Hp infecting first or Py infecting
 102 first). Dots represent the raw data, the boxes represent the interquartile range (IQR), the horizontal
 103 lines the median, and whiskers the range of data within 1.5 the IQR.
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105 Table S7. General linear model investigating the changes in spleen mass (log mg) in single Py infected
 106 and coinfecting (Hp+Py, Hp-7+Py, Hp-28+Py) mice. We report the type III sum of squares, degrees of
 107 freedom (df), the F and p values. The R² of the model is 0.92. N = 118 individuals.
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Source of variation	Type III SS	df	F	p
Treatment	0.49	3,106	12.47	<0.0001
Time	15.08	2,106	580.71	<0.0001
Treatment*Time	0.76	6,106	9.73	<0.0001

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113 Figure S5. Changes in log₁₀ transformed spleen mass (mg) over the course of the infection (for the
114 coinfection groups, time p.i. refers to the time post last infection); a) Changes in spleen mass for single
115 Py infected mice and coinfecting (Hp+Py, Hp-7+Py, Hp-28+Py) mice; b) Changes in spleen mass for single
116 Hp infected and coinfecting (Py-14+Hp, Py-28+Hp) mice. Dots represent the raw data, the boxes
117 represent the interquartile range (IQR), the horizontal lines the median, and whiskers the range of data
118 within 1.5 the IQR.

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121 Table S8. General linear model investigating the changes in spleen mass (log mg) in non-infected, single
122 Py infected and coinfectd (simultaneous infection and Hp first) mice. We report the type III sum of
123 squares, degrees of freedom (df), the F and p values. The R² of the model is 0.94. N = 148 individuals.
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Source of variation	Type III SS	df	F	P
Treatment	16.74	2,139	558.07	<0.0001
Time	9.49	2,139	316.5	<0.0001
Time* Treatment	2.86	4,139	47.65	<0.0001

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127 Table S9. General linear model investigating the changes in spleen mass (log mg) in single Hp infected
128 and coinfectd (Py-14+Hp, Py-28+Hp) mice. We report the type III sum of squares, degrees of freedom
129 (df), the F and p values. The R² of the model is 0.92. N = 108 individuals.
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Source of variation	Type III SS	df	F	p
Treatment	3.66	2,96	259.23	<0.0001
Time	1.61	3,96	75.93	<0.0001
Time*Treatment	2.13	6,96	50.44	<0.0001

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133 Table S10. General linear model investigating the changes in spleen mass (log mg) in non-infected,
134 single Hp infected and coinfecting (Py first) mice. We report the type III sum of squares, degrees of
135 freedom (df), the F and p values. The R² of the model is 0.82. N = 148 individuals.
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Source of variation	Type III SS	df	F	p
Treatment	8.26	2,136	202.54	<0.0001
Time	0.51	3,136	8.42	<0.0001
Time*Treatment	2.00	6,136	16.36	<0.0001

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139 Table S11. General linear model investigating the changes in spleen mass (log mg) in coinfecting mice
140 depending on the order of infection (Hp first or Py first). We report the type III sum of squares, degrees
141 of freedom (df), the F and p values. The R² of the model is 0.76. N = 117 individuals.
142

Source of variation	Type III SS	df	F	p
Treatment	1.69	1,111	70.43	<0.0001
Time	1.04	2,111	21.60	<0.0001
Time*Treatment	5.87	2,111	122.29	<0.0001

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146 Figure S6. Effect of infection and coinfection on liver damage. a) Levels of aspartate aminotransferase
 147 (AST, ng/ml) in the plasma at day 21 p.i. in non-infected and single (Hp, Py) infected mice; b) AST level
 148 in plasma of non-infected, single Py infected and coinfecting (simultaneous infection and Hp first)
 149 groups at day 21 p.i.; c) AST level in plasma of non-infected, single Hp infected and coinfecting (Py first)
 150 groups at day 21 p.i.; d) AST level in plasma of coinfecting mice, depending on the order of the infection
 151 (Hp infecting first or Py infecting first) at day 21 post-infection. Dots represent the raw data, the boxes
 152 represent the interquartile range (IQR), the horizontal lines the median, and whiskers the range of data
 153 within 1.5 the IQR.

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157 Figure S7. a) Levels of aspartate aminotransferase (AST, ng/ml) in the plasma at day 21 p.i. in single Py
158 infected and coinfecting (Hp+Py, Hp-7+Py, Hp-28+Py) mice; b) AST level in plasma of single Hp infected
159 and coinfecting (Py-14+Hp, Py-28+Hp) mice. Dots represent the raw data, the boxes represent the
160 interquartile range (IQR), the horizontal lines the median, and whiskers the range of data within 1.5
161 the IQR.

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164 Figure S8. Survival curves for single Py infected mice and coinfecting (Hp+Py, Hp-7+Py, Hp-28+Py) mice.

165 Crosses indicate censored observations.

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168 Figure S9. Changes in parasitemia (proportion of iRBCs) in single Py infected mice over time. Dots
 169 represent the raw data, the line corresponds to the fit of a GAM where the level of smoothing was
 170 determined based on the GCV criterion.

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173 Table S12. General linear mixed model investigating the changes in parasitemia (proportion of iRBCs)
 174 in single Py infection and coinfecting (Hp+Py, Hp-7+Py, Hp-28+Py) mice. We report the parameter
 175 estimates with the 95% CI, df (degrees of freedom), F and p values. Mouse ID was included as a random
 176 effect to take into account the non-independence of observations for the same individual over time.
 177 The distribution of errors was modelled using a beta distribution. N = 151 individuals and 665
 178 observations.
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Fixed effects		Estimate	95% CI	df	F	p
Treatment				3,506	8.22	<0.0001
	Py	0				
	Hp+Py	0.94	-0.44/2.32			
	Hp-7+Py	2.91	1.66/4.16			
	Hp-28+Py	0.96	-0.64/2.57			
Time		1.05	0.9/1.2	1,506	486.96	<0.0001
Squared time		-0.03	-0.04/0.02	1,506	226.59	<0.0001
Time*Treatment				3,506	6.48	0.0003
	Py	0				
	Hp+Py	-0.13	-0.34/0.08			
	Hp-7+Py	-0.42	-0.61/-0.22			
	Hp-28+Py	-0.22	-0.46/0.01			
Squared Time*Treatment				3,506	7.51	<0.0001
	Py	0				
	Hp+Py	0.006	-0.001/0.013			
	Hp-7+Py	0.02	0.01/0.024			
	Hp-28+Py	0.012	0.003/0.02			
Random effect		Estimate	SE	z	p	
ID		0.128	0.031	4.19	<0.0001	

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183 Figure S10. a) Changes in parasitemia (proportion of iRBCs) in single Py infected mice and coinfected
 184 (Hp+Py, Hp-7+Py, Hp-28+Py) mice over time. Dots represent the raw data, the lines represent the fit
 185 of the GLMM, and the shaded area around the line the 95% CI; b) As in a) but the lines represent the
 186 fit of a GAM where the level of smoothing was determined based on the GCV criterion; c) Changes in
 187 parasitemia (proportion of iRBCs) in single Py infected and coinfected (simultaneous infection and Hp
 188 first) mice. Dots represent the raw data, the lines correspond to the fit of a GAM where the level of
 189 smoothing was determined based on the GCV criterion.

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193 Figure S11. Changes in RBC counts ($10^6/\mu\text{l}$) over the course of the infection for non-infected and single
 194 (Hp, Py) infected mice. Dots represent the raw data, the lines correspond to the fit of a GAM where
 195 the level of smoothing was determined based on the GCV criterion.

196 Table S13. General linear mixed model investigating the changes in RBC counts ($10^6/\mu\text{l}$) in single Py
 197 infected and coinfecting (Hp+Py, Hp-7+Py, Hp-28+Py) mice. We report the parameter estimates with
 198 the 95% CI, df (degrees of freedom), F and p values. Mouse ID was included as a random effect to take
 199 into account the non-independence of observations for the same individual over time. N = 74
 200 individuals and 371 observations.
 201

Fixed effects		Estimate	95% CI	df	F	P
Treatment				3,285	13.23	<0.0001
	Py	0				
	Hp+Py	0.313	-0.365/0.991			
	Hp-7+Py	-1.56	-2.19/-0.93			
	Hp-28+Py	-0.028	-0.661/0.606			
Time		0.092	-0.116/0.301	1,285	0.34	0.5613
Squared time		-0.096	-0.121/-0.07	1,285	99.84	<0.0001
Cubic time		0.004	0.003/0.005	1,285	162.67	<0.0001
Time*Treatment				3,285	3.76	0.0113
	Py	0				
	Hp+Py	-0.487	-0.821/-0.154			
	Hp-7+Py	0.038	-0.26/0.336			
	Hp-28+Py	-0.052	-0.349/0.246			
Squared Time*Treatment				3,285	2.91	0.0351
	Py	0				
	Hp+Py	0.061	0.02/0.103			
	Hp-7+Py	0.017	-0.019/0.054			
	Hp-28+Py	0.021	-0.015/0.058			
Cubic Time*Treatment				3,285	3.57	0.0146
	Py	0				
	Hp+Py	-0.002	-0.003/-0.0008			
	Hp-7+Py	-0.001	-0.002/0.0002			
	Hp-28+Py	-0.001	-0.002/-0.0001			
Random effect		Estimate	SE	z	p	
ID		0.302	0.078	3.85	<0.0001	

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205 Figure S12. Changes in RBC counts ($10^6/\mu\text{l}$) over the course of the infection. a) Changes in RBCs for
 206 single Py infected and coinfected (Hp+Py, Hp-7+Py, Hp-28+Py) mice. Dots represent the raw data, the
 207 lines represent the fit of the GLMM, and the shaded area around the line the 95% CI; b) Same as a) but
 208 the lines correspond to the fit of a GAM where the level of smoothing was determined based on the
 209 GCV criterion; c) Changes in RBCs for non-infected, single Py infected and coinfected (simultaneous
 210 infection and Hp first) groups. Dots represent the raw data, the lines correspond to the fit of a GAM
 211 where the level of smoothing was determined based on the GCV criterion.

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215 Figure S13. Levels of erythropoietin (EPO, log ng/ml) in the plasma at day 14 and 21 p.i. in single Py
 216 infected and coinfecting (Hp+Py, Hp-7+Py, Hp-28+Py) mice. Dots represent the raw data, the boxes
 217 represent the interquartile range (IQR), the horizontal lines the median, and whiskers the range of data
 218 within 1.5 the IQR.

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222 Figure S14. Changes in mean globular volume (fL) over the course of the infection for non-infected and
 223 single (Hp, Py) infected mice. Dots represent the raw data, the lines correspond to the fit of a GAM
 224 where the level of smoothing was determined based on the GCV criterion.

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227 Table S14. General linear mixed model investigating the changes in mean globular volume (fL) in single
 228 Py infected and coinfecting (Hp+Py, Hp-7+Py Hp-28+Py) mice. We report the parameter estimates with
 229 the 95% CI, df (degrees of freedom), F and p values. Mouse ID was included as a random effect to take
 230 into account the non-independence of observations for the same individual over time. N = 74
 231 individuals and 371 observations.
 232

Fixed effects		Estimate	95% CI	df	F	p
Treatment				3,285	0.41	0.7431
	Py	0				
	Hp+Py	-0.302	-4.06/3.46			
	Hp-7+Py	-1.40	-4.86/2.07			
	Hp-28+Py	0.51	-2.99/4.02			
Time		-3.75	-5.02/-2.49	1,285	80.61	<0.0001
Squared time		0.67	0.51/0.82	1,285	173.66	<0.0001
Cubic time		-0.021	-0.026/-0.016	1,285	159.58	<0.0001
Time*Treatment				3,285	0.99	0.4000
	Py	0				
	Hp+Py	1.50	-0.52/3.53			
	Hp-7+Py	0.97	-0.84/2.77			
	Hp-28+Py	0.13	-1.68/1.94			
Squared Time*Treatment				3,285	1.09	0.3519
	Py	0				
	Hp+Py	-0.22	-0.47/0.03			
	Hp-7+Py	-0.13	-0.35/0.096			
	Hp-28+Py	-0.067	-0.29/0.15			
Cubic Time*Treatment				3,285	1.18	0.3162
	Py	0				
	Hp+Py	0.007	-0.001/0.015			
	Hp-7+Py	0.004	-0.002/0.012			
	Hp-28+Py	0.004	-0.003/0.011			
Random effect		Estimate	SE	z	p	
ID		4.9	1.68	2.91	0.0018	

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238 Figure S15. Changes in mean globular volume (MGV, fL) over the course of the infection. a) Changes in
239 MGV for single Py infected mice and coinfected (Hp+Py, Hp-7+Py, Hp-28+Py) mice. Dots represent the
240 raw data, the lines represent the fit of the GLMM, and the shaded area around the line the 95% CI; b)
241 Same as a) but the lines correspond to the fit of a GAM where the level of smoothing was determined
242 based on the GCV criterion; c) Changes in MGV for single Py infected and coinfected (simultaneous
243 infection and Hp first) groups. Dots represent the raw data, the lines correspond to the fit of a GAM
244 where the level of smoothing was determined based on the GCV criterion.

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248 Figure S16. Changes in RBCs ($10^6/\mu\text{l}$) in coinfecting (Hp-28+Py) mice treated with rEPO or left as control
 249 (PBS). Dots represent the raw data, the lines correspond to the fit of a GAM where the level of
 250 smoothing was determined based on the GCV criterion.

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253 Figure S17. a) Gene expression levels relative to β -actin of *Hmox1* in splenocytes (the lower the delta
 254 ΔCt values the higher the expression) at day 14 p.i. in non-infected, single Py infected and coinfected
 255 (simultaneous infection and Hp first) mice; b) Expression levels of *Hmox1* in splenocytes (the lower the
 256 ΔCt values the higher the expression) at day 14 p.i. in single Py infected and coinfected (Hp+Py,
 257 Hp-7+Py, Hp-28+Py) mice; c) Levels of Heme oxygenase-1 in the plasma (log ng/ml) at day 14 and 21
 258 p.i. in single Py infected and coinfected (Hp+Py, Hp-7+Py, Hp-28+Py) mice; d) proportion of CD163⁺
 259 F4/80⁺ CD11b⁻ at day 14 and 21 p.i. in single Py infected and coinfected (Hp+Py, Hp-7+Py, Hp-28+Py)
 260 mice. Dots represent the raw data, the boxes represent the interquartile range (IQR), the horizontal
 261 lines the median, and whiskers the range of data within 1.5 the IQR.
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 264 Figure S18. Gene expression levels relative to β -actin of a) IFN- γ , b) IL-10, c) TGF- β 1 in splenocytes (the
 265 lower the delta Ct values the higher the expression) at day 3 and 14 p.i. in non-infected, single Py
 266 infected and coinfecting (simultaneous infection and Hp first) mice. Gene expression levels of d) IFN- γ ,
 267 e) IL-10, f) TGF- β 1 in splenocytes (the lower the delta Ct values the higher the expression) at day 3 and
 268 14 p.i. in single Py infected and coinfecting (Hp+Py, Hp-7+Py, Hp-28+Py) mice. Dots represent the raw
 269 data, the boxes represent the interquartile range (IQR), the horizontal lines the median, and whiskers
 270 the range of data within 1.5 the IQR.

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273 Table S15. Generalized linear model with a beta distribution of errors investigating the changes in the
274 proportion of FoxP3⁺ CD4⁺ T cells in single Py infected, and coinfectd (Hp+Py, Hp-7+Py, Hp-28+Py)
275 mice at day 14 and 21 post-infection. We report the degrees of freedom (df), and the F and p values.
276 N = 80 individuals.
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Source of variation	df	F	p
Treatment	3,72	1.50	0.2220
Time	1,72	0.07	0.7865
Treatment*Time	3,72	0.21	0.8917

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284 Figure 19. a) FoxP3⁺ (proportion of CD4⁺) T cells analyzed by flow cytometry over the course of the
 285 infection in single Py infected and coinfecting (Hp+Py, Hp-7+Py, Hp-28+Py) mice; b) CTLA-4⁺ FoxP3⁺
 286 (proportion of CD4⁺) T cells over the course of the infection in single Py infected and coinfecting (Hp+Py,
 287 Hp-7+Py, Hp-28+Py) mice. Dots represent the raw data, the boxes represent the interquartile range
 288 (IQR), the horizontal lines the median, and whiskers the range of data within 1.5 the IQR.
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292 Table S16. Generalized linear model with a beta distribution of errors investigating the changes in the
293 proportion of CTLA-4⁺ FoxP3⁺ CD4⁺ T cells in single Py infected, and coinfecting (Hp+Py, Hp-7+Py, Hp-
294 28+Py) mice at day 14 and 21 post-infection. We report the degrees of freedom (df), and the F and p
295 values. N = 77 individuals.
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Source of variation	df	F	p
Treatment	3,69	2.44	0.0720
Time	1,69	12.16	0.0009
Treatment*Time	3,69	6.97	0.0004

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322 Table S17. List of immune cell populations identified by flow cytometry analysis included in the PCA
 323 and variable loadings on the two principal components (PC1, PC2) at each sampling day. N= 148.
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	Loadings					
	<i>Day 3 p.i.</i>		<i>Day 14 p.i.</i>		<i>Day 21 p.i.</i>	
	<i>PC1</i>	<i>PC2</i>	<i>PC1</i>	<i>PC2</i>	<i>PC1</i>	<i>PC2</i>
CD3 ⁺ (T cells)	-0.899	-0.265	0.756	-0.261	0.368	-0.191
CD4 ⁺ (helper T cells)	-0.118	0.846	-0.143	-0.317	-0.057	-0.715
CD8 ⁺ (cytotoxic T cells)	0.060	-0.883	0.933	0.1305	0.923	-0.086
T-bet ⁺ CD4 ⁺ (Th1 cells)	-0.300	-0.188	-0.372	-0.271	0.311	0.468
RORγt ⁺ CD4 ⁺ (Th17 cells)	0.249	0.343	0.444	0.515	0.569	0.425
GATA-3 ⁺ CD4 ⁺ (Th2 cells)	0.438	0.658	-0.637	0.302	-0.597	-0.077
FoxP3 ⁺ CD4 ⁺ (Treg cells)	0.525	0.320	0.421	-0.182	0.150	-0.659
CD19 ⁺ (B cells)	0.798	0.144	0.604	-0.331	0.759	0.275
T-bet ⁺ CD19 ⁺ Memory B cells	0.125	-0.438	-0.830	-0.137	-0.388	0.591
CD127 ⁺ CD19 ⁺ Immature B cells	0.438	0.573	-0.575	0.527	-0.331	0.674
Ly6G ⁺ LIN (Neutrophils)	0.415	-0.150	-0.751	0.123	-0.778	0.040
MHCII ^{hi} CD11c ^{hi} (Dendritic cells)	-0.743	-0.071	0.258	-0.424	0.854	0.198
F4/80 ⁺ CD11b ⁺ (Macrophages)	0.514	-0.594	-0.100	0.184	0.447	0.525
F4/80 ⁺ CD11b ⁻ (Red pulp macrophages, RPM)	-0.234	0.616	-0.309	0.666	-0.001	-0.206
CD163 ⁺ F4/80 ⁺ CD11b ⁻ MHCII ⁺ (scavenger RPM)	-0.833	0.077	0.901	0.275	0.887	-0.264
CD163 ⁻ F4/80 ⁺ CD11b ⁻ MHCII ⁺ (other RPM)	0.823	-0.071	-0.919	-0.253	-0.880	0.270
F4/80 ^{-/low} CD11b ⁺ (Monocytes)	-0.729	0.279	0.869	-0.047	0.776	-0.225
Ly6C ^{hi} F4/80 ^{-/low} CD11b ⁺ MHCII ^{-/low} (Monocytes)	0.628	-0.237	-0.624	0.173	-0.651	0.177
Ly6C ^{int} F4/80 ^{-/low} CD11b ⁺ MHCII ^{-/low} (Monocytes)	-0.077	0.222	-0.255	-0.741	-0.400	-0.511
Ly6C ^{-/low} F4/80 ^{-/low} CD11b ⁺ MHCII ^{-/low} (Monocytes)	-0.413	0.106	0.750	0.352	0.7875	0.2577

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